

NAPOLEON CADASTERS AND LAND REGISTERS
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Abstract: In the current developing period, for the development of a certain field, studying and analyzing the world experience in the field and applying its advantages in the field in our country is one of the most effective methods.

Key words: Department, register, standard cadastre, tax.

Napoleon I improved the land registry and made it more modern.

Napoleon Land Registry Map,

The general land registry known as "Napoleon" was established by the Finance Act of September 15, 1807 (decree of January 27, 1808). Like the land register of the mass and nature of the vegetation, it allowed taxation by distribution, taking into account the rental value of each plot and the income of each owner.

"Plot" means a plot of land with the same type of crops and belonging to the same owner. To establish a land registry, land parcels in each commune were surveyed, mapped, and classified according to soil fertility. Along with each homestead owner, their built (houses and buildings) or unbuilt (for example, meadows, vineyards, fields, etc.) properties are identified. About 40,000 communes, that is, land on several hundred million plots of land

The project, which includes measuring, evaluating and drawing plots, will be

carried out over several decades.

In addition to fiscal purposes, cadastral documents also had an administrative purpose: to prove property ownership. The land registry consisted of two main types of documents: topographic land documents (plans) and handwritten land documents (registers). In the 19th century, three documents were developed: the plan, the section status and the matrix. Plot plans show each plot of land in the commune, and each plot is numbered. In the status of the department, the land plots in the department are indicated by numbers, and for each of them, the name of the owner, nomenclature and tax information on the date of the creation of the land register are indicated.

Cadastral matrices were registers that listed the parcels belonging to each owner.

For each commune, cadastral plans are made in two copies: the minute plan is kept in the commune and the chief surveyor worked, and the "department" or "prefecture" copy is kept in the property tax office. belonged to the commune (each district had one office). The last copy is kept in the archives of the Department.

Change 100 years after creation

Plans for the Napoleonic Land Registry were designed to be clear and did not need to be updated. However, the land registry was redesigned from the 1930s to the 1970s. Revision by update (since 1930) was carried out on the basis of the old map (old boundaries were deleted and replaced with new ones). Faced with the difficulty of carrying out such a revision, from 1941, a complete overhaul of the map was carried out. New readings accepted. Made new maps, new section status and new matrices. The aim was to revise the property valuation used as a basis for taxation. One of the reforms was implemented in 1955 after the obligation to publish land registry data in the mortgage register came into force. As a result of these reforms, the old references in the land registry were canceled and a new

numbering system was introduced: now the sections are marked with a double letter (for example, "AB").

MAIN PART

The Napoleonic cadastre or the old cadastre or cadastral plan of 1812 is a single and centralized cadastral section established in France by the law of September 15, 1807, from the "standard cadastre" established on November 2, 1802 .. Combining about one hundred million sections. the single map is the first legal and tax instrument that allows fair taxation of land contributions from citizens.

Inheriting the plans of the Terriers, which were very different in terms of concept and even units of measurement, it was issued by topographical photography methods and was revised by law on April 16, 1930. In the course of this study, studying the use of land resources and areas of land cadastre in countries with a developed land market, applying the experience of these countries in practice, which is suitable for our conditions, has already given very good results and will not lose its effectiveness in the future. . Within the framework of the research topic, below, the land cadastre management of several foreign countries, the procedure for using the database was reviewed and analyzed.

1) Republic of France. The foundations of modern land cadastre in foreign countries appeared in the 20th century. Among them, the most well-structured is the French land cadastre. The French land cadastre is a consistent system for determining land tax, accounting for the quantity and quality of land. The main unit of value in the French land cadastre is the plot of land. More precisely, the French land cadastre serves three purposes.

That is:

- to draw up cadastral plans;
- identification and description of land plots;

➤ to determine land valuation and land tax norms.

Currently, the "Napoleonic cadastre" is used as the main source. In 1848, all of France was registered. As for the cartography of the country, we are in the midst of a boom in the production of maps produced by the General Staff Officer Corps, commonly known as "staff maps." It should be noted that this monument of French cartography for the creation of planimetry is mainly based on the direct use of cadastral maps of their collection tables.

In the second half of the 19th century, several important events took place, except for the development of technology and measuring instruments. However, decades later, one theme emerges: the issue of plan renewal. It was never intended to be a plan update. It was even illegal! There were only a few deviations from the rule to mitigate some situations, for example, taking into account changes in the boundaries of municipalities. Then the rule was to update the cadastral matrices without touching the plan. The desire not to update the plan was mainly due to costs ... Since the cadastral plan was only a fiscal document, there was no interest in graphically monitoring the evolution of the property.

For example; The main purpose of the French cadastral system is to ensure land taxation. To this day, it serves as a fiscal system: its information is the basis for calculating property taxes related to various land and immovable property. But

In France, together with all the legal annexes, the land register cannot provide complete systematic information on the entire territory of the country. Large cities such as Paris, Lille, Marseille have created private multi-purpose cadastral systems of their areas. Half of them, basically

in rural areas, they use old plans from the Napoleonic era, as well as plans drawn up between the 1930s and 1960s. and 1960 - they are generally not accurate enough and contain random errors

the other half consists of new plans, called "regular" because they meet official technical standards; they are known for high accuracy of cartographic

images, but not enough to meet some needs;

During the Napoleonic Empire, there was a need to create a useful tool for the census and especially for the taxation of the territory, and therefore the extraordinary initiative of the Cadastre began. It was, first of all, a very important innovation in the fiscal management of the state, and at the same time it encouraged and accepted great achievements in the representation of the territory. The main features of the Napoleonic cadastre, which are noticeable in the maps that have survived to our days, are the precise description of the territory and the modernity of the geodetic technique. In addition, the metric decimal system was adopted for surveying the entire empire.

In the territory of the province of Savona, between 1808 and 1815, the measurement and collection procedures were carried out under the direct leadership of Chabrol de Volcic, prefect of the department of Montenotte, named after Napoleon.

increased. The process was based on a system of topographic measurements and a system of estimating the various crops grown in the area, initially classified according to the mass of cultivation and later changed to a particle form starting in 1808.

CONCLUSION

In the current developing period, one of the most effective ways to develop a certain field is to study and analyze the world experience in the field and apply its advantages in our country within this field. Based on the above opinions and considerations, economic entities operating in the territory of the republic will be provided with a comprehensive land information base of land plots. Regulation of the state land tax system creates an opportunity to timely fulfill the tasks set by the government in this regard. In addition, by familiarizing with foreign experience, creating a land cadastre information system, engaged in agriculture and managing this field,

it is envisaged to create a reliable system of administrative and economic services at various levels that solves issues related to planning and control.

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